

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Serving as a Lead Organ Contact

Responsibilities of editors for Human Reference Atlas digital objects

Authors: Nancy Ruschman, Elizabeth G. Record¹

Approved by: Katy Börner¹ (July 16, 2025)

¹ Department of Intelligent Systems Engineering, Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA.

Introduction

Every six months, a new release of Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is published on the Human Reference Atlas Portal (<https://humanatlas.io>). This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) details the tasks of the Lead Organ Contact during the authoring, validation, and release process. See the HRA Digital Objects Release Process SOP (in press) for a more comprehensive overview of the process. Individual SOPs detailing how each digital object type is authored can be found on the Standard Operating Procedures page of the HRA Portal (<https://humanatlas.io/standard-operating-procedures>).

This document serves as a reference for Lead Organ Contacts, and for those who work with them to ensure timely releases. A basic familiarity with the HRA and the digital objects that comprise it is assumed (Börner et al. 2021; 2025).

Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Lead** is responsible for identifying LOCs, prioritizing organs and digital objects, and ensuring a timely, high-quality, and on-budget release.

The **HRA Project Manager (PM)** is responsible for coordinating tasks, assisting with communication between parties, and ensuring digital objects are passed between those who create them, those who review them, and those who validate them.

Lead Organ Contacts (LOC) are responsible for ensuring that all digital objects related to the organ of focus are prepared in time for the release. They also incorporate feedback generated during the external expert review and automatic validation. There is only one Lead Organ Contact per organ, but one expert might serve as Lead Organ Contact for multiple organs.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Lead	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu
HRA Project Manager	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu

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Lead Organ Contact (LOC)	various	various
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Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Procedures

Introduction to HRAorg documents

Lead Organ Contacts use HRA organizational documents (HRAorg docs) to access and share information about their organ of focus for the upcoming release. The document is prepared by the HRA PM and includes links to all digital objects that will be part of the upcoming release.

Digital object types might include:

- ASCT+B tables
- 3D reference objects
- 2D functional tissue units
- Cell type annotation crosswalks
- Organ Mapping Antibody Panels (OMAPs)
- Antibody Validation Reports (AVRs)
- Landmark organs
- Millitomes

Lead Organ Contact actions

- Once you have committed to serving as Lead Organ Contact, review the HRAorg document shared by the HRA PM (January/July).
- Inform the HRA Project Manager what new and revised digital objects you expect to incorporate in the next HRA release.
- Identify and secure additional subject matter expertise, if needed.
- Author and/or revise HRA digital objects (January-March/July-September)
- Present in the HRA Working Group to obtain community feedback before the April 1/October 1 deadline.
- Confirm that all digital objects are complete and ready for validation by April 1/October 1.
- Respond to validation results during the validation period (April/October).
- Approve all digital objects for publication in HRA release by May 1/November 1.

A general release timeline can be [found here](#).

References and Resources

Börner, Katy, Philip D. Blood, Jonathan C. Silverstein, Matthew Ruffalo, Rahul Satija, Sarah A. Teichmann, Gloria J. Pryhuber, et al. 2025. "Human BioMolecular Atlas Program (HuBMAP): 3D Human Reference Atlas Construction and Usage." *Nature Methods*, March, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-024-02563-5>.

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Börner, Katy, Sarah A. Teichmann, Ellen M. Quardokus, et al. 2021. "Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas." *Nature Cell Biology* 23 (11): 1117–28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41556-021-00788-6>.

Glossary

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D spatial objects (e.g., anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials, and surface color and texture. They are created by medical illustrators with the involvement of subject matter experts following standard operating procedures.

ASCT+B Tables: ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types, and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid, or metabolic markers). Cellular identity is supported by scientific evidence and linked to ontologies.

Antibody Validation Report (AVR): Document providing details on the characterization of individual antibodies for multiplexed antibody-based imaging assays. These details include target information (e.g., target name, UniProt accession number, and antibody information (e.g., RRID, host organism, vendor, catalog number, lot number). AVRs also provide details on controls used for antibody characterization (positive and negative tissues, cell lines, isotype controls, etc), exemplar imaging data, and information on other antibodies tested.

Crosswalk: An ontological mapping of terms in the Human Reference Atlas digital objects (e.g., 2/3D reference objects, OMAPs, Azimuth references) to ontology terms in the ASCT+B tables.

Digital Object (DO): Unit of information that includes properties (attributes or characteristics of the object) and may also include methods (means of performing operations on the object).

Functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization, i.e. a set of cells, that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ.

Human Reference Atlas Organizational Document (HRAorg doc): HRA organizational documents, or HRAorg docs, serve to collect and share information about each organ in the upcoming HRA release. The documents include links to all digital objects related to a single organ that is either being authored or revised during the current release cycle.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The HRA is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The HRA provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

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Organ Mapping Antibody Panel (OMAP): A comprehensive panel of curated antibodies that identifies the major anatomical structures and cell types in a specific organ. The selected antibodies are optimized for a tissue preservation method (i.e., fixed, frozen) and multiplexed imaging modality (e.g., CODEX, Cell DIVE) through published protocols (protocols.io) and AVR.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g., plain English).

Subject Matter Expert (SME): An SME is a person with extensive knowledge about a given topic.

Acknowledgments

The Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is under active development by the Indiana University Mapping Component as part of the HuBMAP HIVE, SenNet CODCC, KPMP, and GUDMAP efforts with expert input by the HRA Editorial Board and in close collaboration with experts from more than 18 other consortia. Data was provided by HuBMAP and other Tissue Mapping Centers. This research has been supported by the NIH Common Fund through the Office of Strategic Coordination/Office of the NIH Director under awards OT2OD033756 and OT2OD026671, by the Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet) Consortium through the Consortium Organization and Data Coordinating Center (CODCC) under award number U24CA268108, and by the NIDDK under awards U24DK135157 and U01DK133090. The work has also been supported by the Kidney Precision Medicine Project grant U2CDK114886, and the NIH National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), Department of Health and Human Services under BCBB Support Services Contract HHSN316201300006W/HHSN27200002, as well as the American Dental Association Science and Research Institute and the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research's MacMillan Multiscale Human program. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.

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Appendix A

HRAorg Document Template

<insert release> HRA Org Document for <Organ>

Lead Organ Contact (LOC)

<insert name and email>

As lead organ expert, we would like to ask that you serve as the main point of contact for all Digital Objects (DOs). Please answer questions in a timely manner and work with the HRA team to maintain consistency, accuracy, and completeness of organ-specific content. See current SOP: Responsibilities of the Lead Organ Contact <insert link>.

For questions, please contact infoccf@iu.edu.

Official Approval

As LOC, initial each digital object when it is complete and ready for validation and again when the final version is approved for publication, see the [HRA Release Timeline](#).

Digital Object Type	Ready for Validation (initial and date)	Approved for Publication (initial and date)
ASCT+B Table		
2D FTU Illustrations		
3D Reference Organs		
Crosswalks		
OMAPs		
AVRs		
Millitomes		
Landmark Organs		

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ASCT+B Tables

Current ASCT+B Tables: <https://humanatlas.io/asctb-tables>

New table that should be used to make changes for upcoming release: <insert link>

ASCT+B External Reviewer Comments

Table <insert version> was sent out to external experts and reviewer comments are provided below. Please consider these comments when making revisions. Please state which reviews you incorporated (e.g., all reviewers, reviewer #1 only, none). If reviews were not addressed, please provide your rationale here:

Reviewer #1

<insert comments>

Reviewer #2

<insert comments>

2D Functional Tissue Units (FTU)

Current FTU illustrations: <https://humanatlas.io/2d-ftu-illustrations>

Current Crosswalk: [Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers \(ASCT+B\) Tables to 2D Functional Tissue Unit \(FTU\) Reference Object Library Crosswalk, Latest](#)

Please suggest revisions to existing and/or new FTU illustrations:

2D FTU External Review Comments

Table <insert version> was sent out to external experts and reviewer comments are provided below. Please consider these comments when making revisions. Please state which reviews you incorporated (e.g., all reviewers, reviewer #1 only, none). If reviews were not addressed, please provide your rationale here:

Reviewer #1

<insert comments>

Reviewer #2

<insert comments>

3D Reference Organ

Current FTU illustrations: [Human Reference Atlas Portal](#)

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Current Crosswalk: [Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers \(ASCT+B\) Tables to 3D Reference Object Library Crosswalk, Latest](#)

Please suggest revisions to existing and/or new 3D Reference Organs:

3D Reference Objects External Review Comments

Table <insert version> was sent out to external experts and reviewer comments are provided below. Please consider these comments when making revisions. Please state which reviews you incorporated (e.g., all reviewers, reviewer #1 only, none). If reviews were not addressed, please provide your rationale here:

Reviewer #1

<insert comments>

Reviewer #2

<insert comments>

OMAP (Organ Mapping Antibody Panels)

Current OMAPs: <https://humanatlas.io/omap>

<insert link to new or revised OMAPs>

Please review existing OMAPs and/or add new OMAPs and any questions or comments here:

AVR (Antibody Validation Report)

Current AVRs: <https://avr.hubmapconsortium.org> (not all are listed)

<insert link to new or revised AVR>

Please review the AVRs and/or add new AVRs add any questions or comments here:

Cell Type Annotation Crosswalks

Crosswalks: <https://humanatlas.io/cell-type-annotations>

Current Crosswalks: [Catalog for https://lod.humanatlas.io/ctann](https://lod.humanatlas.io/ctann)

Please review the crosswalks and add any questions or comments here:

Validation: Parsing Files for HRA KG Construction

Bruce W. Herr II is using the 200+ HRA DOs to compile the HRA KG, see details in (Bueckle et al. 2025). The following issues were encountered when reading your files:

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<insert comments>

Validation: Existing Ontologies

EBI is running weekly validation reports, see (Caron et al. 2024) for details. Review the validation page for your ASCT+B table at

<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-validation-tools/>. There are three links to review:

- General Report
- ASCT+B as Graph
- Report Changes

Please review the validation reports and add any questions or comments here:

Validation: Vasculature

Griffin Weber, Harvard Medical School has reviewed the HRA DOs and the following changes were made:

<insert comments>

Add any questions and comments you have here:

RUI Registrations

There exist <insert number> registered datasets for your organ.

<insert link to existing RUI Registrations in organ specific EUI>

Please review the RUI registrations and add any questions or comments here:

Millitomes

There exist <insert number> millitomes for your organ, see <https://humanatlas.io/millitome>.

Please review the millitome(s) and add any questions or comments here:

Landmark Organs

There exist <insert number> landmark organs for your organ, see [Catalog for https://lod.humanatlas.io/landmark](https://lod.humanatlas.io/landmark).

Please review these and add any questions or comments here:

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SOPs are found at <https://humanatlas.io/standard-operating-procedures>

References

Bueckle, Andreas, Bruce W. Herr, Josef Hardi, Ellen M. Quardokus, Mark A. Musen, and Katy Börner. 2025. "Construction, Deployment, and Usage of the Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph." *Scientific Data* 12 (1): 1100. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-05183-6>.

Caron, Anita Reane, Aleix Puig-Barbe, Ellen M. Quardokus, et al. 2024. "A General Strategy for Generating Expert-Guided, Simplified Views of Ontologies." Preprint, bioRxiv, December 18. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.13.628309>.